

University of
Southern
Queensland

Circular Economy Opportunities for Waste Glass Fibre Reinforced Sucker Rod Guides

Chundu Gyem Tamang

PhD Candidate

University of Southern Queensland

SUCKER ROD GUIDES

Figure: Rod guide application [2]

Figure: Different types of artificial lift technologies [1]

Guide material

- PA 6 (Nylon 6) with 25% glass fibre reinforcement
- Downhole operating temperature: 70-100° C
- Weight: 150-300 grams

Why are Rod-Guides needed?

Figure: Typical failures of sucker rod pumping system [3]

Well maintenance cost = 50-85% due to sucker rod/tubing wear
Well downtime = Production loss

**Rod string
centralization/Prevention
of rod buckling**

Figure: Rod string buckling [2]

Why are Rod-Guides needed?

Paraffin Control

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

SUCKER ROD GUIDES

Figure: Different guide configurations [4]

Guide Material (PA6)

- Recycling rate of PA in 2019 – 2% [5]
- PA 6 – 2/3 of total PA production [6]

Failure of rod guides

Exposure to contaminants

Physical degradation

Exposure to high temperature

Top Section

Mid-Section

Bottom Section

Characterisation

Materials

Table 1. Properties of 25% glass fibre reinforced Nylon 6

Typical Properties	Units	Test Method	Values
Mechanical Properties			
Tensile Yield Strength	MPa	ISO 527-2/1A	120
Flexural Strength	MPa	ISO 178	190
Flexural Modulus	MPa	ISO 178	7100
Notched IZOD Impact Strength @ +23°C	kJ/m ²	ISO 180/1A	6
Physical Properties			
Density	g/cm ³	ISO 1183	1.31
Moulding Shrinkage, 3.17 mm bar	%	-	0.2-0.8
Thermal Properties			
HDT at 1.8 MPa load	°C	ASTM D-648	204
Melting Point (DSC)	°C	ISO 3146	220

Sample Preparation

Figure 1: Nylon 6 rod guide dimensions, cutting and preparation of samples without removing surface contamination

Surface roughness measurement

Figure 2: (a) Virgin Nylon 6 rod guide, (b) Exposed Nylon 6 rod guide with increased roughness at the vane section

Figure 3: Profile and roughness parameters of the exposed Nylon 6 from rod guide vane

Figure 4. Roughness profile of exposed Nylon 6 from rod guide body

Figure 5. Roughness profile of virgin Nylon 6 from rod guide vane

Figure 6. Roughness profile of virgin Nylon 6 from rod guide body

XRD test

Figure: XRD diffractograms of two guide samples

Findings:

- Crystallinity of guide 1= 47.81
- Crystallinity of guide 2= 48.94
- Alpha/gamma of guide 1= 8.66
- Alpha/gamma of guide 2= 8.39
- Alpha phase is the predominant crystal phase

Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX)

Figure: UVD image of guide 1

Figure: EDX of guide 1

Guide 1

- Few voids
- Rough surface with signs of perforations
- Fe, O, S, Si, Al, and Ca the major contaminants

Polished cross-section

- Al, Na, Mg, K, Ca, Si and O typical of GF
- GF concentration lesser at the surface
- No foreign materials detected below ~10 um

Chemical Properties

Name of Chemical	Potential Effect on Nylon 6	Reference	Actual Observed Effect on exposed glass fibre reinforced Nylon 6
Ethanedial	Can react with amine groups, leading to cross-linking and change in properties.	(26,45)	No alteration of amide groups
Pentanedial	High likelihood of cross linking with amide groups (For example, -CH ₂ - deformation vibration at 1364 cm ⁻¹)	(26,46)	No cross linking with amide groups observed
Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH)	Possible hydrolysis of amide bonds and subsequent degradation	(26,43)	No recorded hydrolysis
Acetic Acid	Can cause surface degradation of Nylon 6 at higher concentrations	(26,47,48)	No effect
Methanol	Can cause swelling of Nylon 6 even at 23° C	(26,43)	Swelling or chemical changes absent
Sulfuric Acid	High likelihood of material degradation (including corrosion and swelling)	(26,40,43)	No changes in chemical structure observed
Hydrochloric Acid	High likelihood of material degradation	(36,39,34)	No effect on the chemical structure
Potassium Chloride	Prolonged exposure can cause material deterioration	(26,49)	No effect observed after 24 months of exposure
Ethanol	Can cause swelling or plasticisation of Nylon 6 (For example, Nylons can soften by 1.5-2.5 factor from ethanol absorption)	(34,36,42)	No effect on chemical properties recorded

Category	Chemical	Concentration	Temperature	Resistance	Remarks	Reference
Hydrocarbons	Benzene	Pure	23°C	Excellent	Excellent resistance to aromatic hydrocarbons	(40)
	Toluene	Pure	23°C	Excellent	No swelling or degradation	(41)
	Xylene	Pure	23°C	Excellent	Suitable for extended exposure in oil wells	(42)
	Cyclohexane	Pure	23°C	Excellent	Good compatibility during petrochemical processes	(40)
	Diesel	Mixed Hydrocarbons	Varies	Excellent	Minimal effect on Nylon 6	(43)
	Crude Oil	Mixed Hydrocarbons	Varies	Good	Good performance which is varied by compositions	(42)
Acids	Hydrochloric Acid	≤20%	23°C	Poor	Degradation of Nylon 6 through attack of strong mineral acids	(44)
	Sulphuric Acid	≤10%	23°C	Poor		(42)
	Acetic Acid	≤80%	23°C	Poor	Limited resistance which causes degradation at higher concentrations	(41)
Bases	Sodium Hydroxide	≤10%	23°C	Poor	Minor degradation in dilute solutions which changes to major damage in higher concentration or temperatures	(43)
	Potassium Hydroxide	≤10%	23°C	Good	Only recommended in dilute solutions at ambient conditions	(41)
Alcohols	Methanol	Pure	23°C	Good	No significant effect	(42)
	Ethanol	≤96%	23°C	Good	Good resistance	(40)
Gases	Carbon Dioxide	Gaseous	23°C	Excellent	No observed effect	(43)
	Hydrogen Sulphide	Gaseous	23°C	Poor	Only tolerant in low concentration exposures and can cause degradation during prolonged exposures	(44)
Brine Solution	Sodium Chloride	Saturated	23°C	Good	Good resistance to chemical attack from brine but prolonged exposure and higher temperatures can affect mechanical performance	(41)
Aromatic Ketones	Acetone	Pure	23°C	Poor	Can cause swelling during prolonged exposure	(40)
Others	Lubricating Oils	Mixed Hydrocarbons	Varies	Excellent	Nylon 6 maintain dimensional stability	(43)
	Drilling Fluids	Mixed	Varies	Good	Dependent on various compositions	(42)

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Figure 7. FTIR spectra of used Nylon 6 samples from Well No.1

Figure 8. FTIR spectra of used Nylon 6 samples from Well No.2

Figure 9. Comparison of FTIR results from virgin Nylon 6 with used Nylon 6 obtained from the top, middle, and bottom well sections

Band location (cm^{-1})	Assignment	Reference
3287	N-H stretching vibration from amide groups	(35-37)
2924	C-H stretching vibration from methylene groups	(38,39)
2855	C-H stretching vibration from methylene groups	(38,39)
1628	C=O stretching (Amide I)	(35-37)
1535	N-H bending with C-N stretching vibrations (Amide II)	(35-37)

Surface Contaminants

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. (a) Visible surface contamination on used samples, (b) FTIR results of the contaminants

Figure 11. Surface contaminants under the Olympus Microscope

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Figure 12. SEM of virgin Nylon 6

Figure 13. SEM of exposed Nylon 6

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

(a)

(b)

Figure 14. DSC test results of (a) Samples from well no.1 and (b) Samples from well no.2

Fibre Length Distribution

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 15. Fibre Length Distribution of (a) Virgin Sample, (b) Samples from well no.1, and (c) Samples from well no.2

Experimental study on residue glass fibres

Figure 16. Microscopic view of residue glass fibres after burn off test

Figure 17. FTIR of residue glass fibres

THANK YOU!!!!